

Social-Emotional and Spiritual Growth of Key Stage I Learners in Congressional District IV, Division of Batangas

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine the level of social-emotional and spiritual growth of Key Stage I learners as assessed by their teachers, as well as the challenges encountered in sustaining these aspects in the classroom. Specifically, it focused on learners' social-emotional development in terms of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship skills, and their spiritual growth in terms of values and moral development, sense of purpose and meaning, respect for others' beliefs, and participation in spiritual or values-related activities. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, utilizing a structured questionnaire to gather data from selected Key Stage I teachers. The collected data were analyzed using weighted mean and Pearson r to determine both the level of manifestation and the significant relationships between variables.

The findings revealed that both social-emotional and spiritual growth of learners were manifested at an above average level across all dimensions. Among the indicators, learners were particularly strong in expressing appreciation for others, participating respectfully in discussions, and demonstrating courage in admitting mistakes. However, relatively lower ratings were noted in areas such as expressing personal strengths and limitations, managing impulses, appreciating others' contributions, demonstrating honesty in small situations, and actively engaging in reflection or prayer. Correlation analysis showed significant relationships between social-emotional domains and spiritual growth, particularly in values formation, sense of purpose, and respect for others' beliefs, while no significant relationship was found with participation in spiritual activities. Teachers also agreed that they encounter challenges related to time constraints, diverse learner backgrounds, emotional readiness, and external influences, which affect the consistent integration of these competencies in the classroom.

Keywords: *social-emotional growth, spiritual development, Key Stage I learners, values formation, teacher challenges*

Introduction

The development of learners in Basic Education does not only rest on the mastery of academic subjects but also on their holistic growth as individuals. Beyond intellectual abilities, children are expected to acquire social-emotional skills that help them understand themselves, manage emotions, relate with others, and build positive relationships. In the same way, spiritual growth nurtures their values, sense of meaning, and respect for beliefs, guiding them toward moral and purposeful lives. These dimensions of growth form the foundation of character, resilience, and balanced learning that are essential for navigating both school and life.

In today's classrooms, teachers increasingly recognize that education is not simply about producing high test scores but also about fostering learners who are socially responsible and spiritually grounded. Elementary education is a crucial stage where values and interpersonal habits are shaped. It is during this period that children begin to experience interactions that build empathy, self-awareness, respect, and faith. When nurtured, these qualities empower young learners to face challenges, contribute positively to their communities, and grow into responsible citizens.

The intention of this study is to bridge these gaps by examining the social-emotional and spiritual growth of Key Stage I learners through assessment of teachers in Congressional District IV, Division of Batangas. By situating the investigation in a local context, the research seeks to capture authentic experiences and challenges that teachers encounter in sustaining these aspects of growth. The study also aims to propose practical interventions and programs based on the realities observed in classrooms, thereby aligning educational strategies with the developmental needs of learners.

In the local context, teachers in Batangas witness firsthand how learners' social-emotional and spiritual needs intersect with the realities of their environment. While many children display enthusiasm for learning, some struggle with self-awareness and self-control, often affecting their behavior in class. Others face difficulties in forming healthy peer relationships, influenced by exposure to technology, changing family structures, and social pressures. These challenges highlight the importance of schools in guiding children to develop empathy, responsibility, and resilience.

At the same time, spiritual formation among learners is becoming increasingly complex. While schools continue to promote values education, teachers observe varied levels of participation and interest in spiritual or values-related activities. The growing diversity of beliefs and lifestyles in communities also brings both opportunities and challenges in promoting respect for others' faiths. In Congressional District IV of Batangas, where cultural traditions and religious practices remain strong, schools face the task of nurturing learners who can uphold moral values while embracing inclusivity.

This study, therefore, seeks to examine the social-emotional and spiritual growth of Key Stage I learners as assessed by teachers in Congressional District IV, Division of Batangas. By

understanding teachers' insights, the study aims to provide a clearer picture of learners' developmental needs, the challenges educators face, and the ways schools can further support holistic education. Through this approach, the study addresses existing gaps by giving voice to teachers and highlighting the intersection of socio-emotional and spiritual development in a specific Philippine setting. The findings will not only enrich the body of literature but also provide concrete insights that can guide schools, administrators, and education officials in strengthening holistic programs that respond to both the academic and formative dimensions of learning.

The results of this research, not only teachers and learners may benefit but also administrators, policymakers, and parents. By identifying strengths and gaps in the social-emotional and spiritual growth of learners, programs and interventions can be designed to support holistic development in the elementary years. In the long run, this contributes to building a generation of students who are academically competent, emotionally balanced, spiritually grounded, and socially responsible.

This study aimed to examine the social-emotional and spiritual growth of Key Stage I learners in Congressional District IV, Division of Batangas. It seeks to describe learners' developmental levels in these two domains, identify the challenges teachers face in fostering them, and propose possible programs or interventions that can enhance learners' holistic growth. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of social-emotional growth of elementary learners as assessed by their teachers in terms of;
 - 1.1. self-awareness;
 - 1.2. self-management;
 - 1.3. social awareness; and
 - 1.4. relationship skills?
2. What is the level of spiritual growth of elementary learners as assessed by the respondents with respect to;
 - 2.1. values and moral development;
 - 2.2. sense of purpose and meaning;
 - 2.3. respect for others' beliefs; and
 - 2.4. participation in values-related activities?
3. Is there significant relationship between the assessment on the level of social-emotional growth of the learners on their level of spiritual growth?
4. What challenges do teachers encounter in sustaining social-emotional and spiritual growth among elementary learners?
5. Based on the results, what sustainable development activities may be proposed?

Literature Review

Weissberg et al. (2022) explained that activities such as journaling, mindfulness exercises, classroom check-ins, collaborative projects, and storytelling circles help learners recognize emotions, regulate behavior, and build empathy toward others. These practices also improve

resilience, confidence, and communication skills, allowing children to participate more actively in school and develop positive relationships. It emphasized that social-emotional learning is not an additional subject but a foundational component of academic and personal success.

Ho and Funk (2023) explained that teachers play a significant role in nurturing learners' emotional health through warm relationships, positive classroom interactions, and structured SEL activities. Strategies such as brain breaks, peace corners, role-playing, gratitude journals, and guided discussions were identified as effective ways of helping learners develop emotional regulation and interpersonal skills. They stressed that meaningful social-emotional development occurs when schools, teachers, and families work together to provide consistent support and opportunities for reflection, cooperation, and empathy.

Foundation Worldview (2025) emphasized that spiritual growth is nurtured through intentional guidance, routines, and meaningful experiences such as prayer, worship, Bible reading, reflection, and acts of service. These practices help children strengthen their values, moral development, sense of purpose, and respect for others' beliefs. They explained that spiritual growth develops gradually through instruction, modeling, and personal experiences, allowing learners to internalize values and apply them in their daily lives.

Albers (2023) explained that parents, teachers, and faith communities play a vital role in shaping children's spirituality by modeling integrity, compassion, and faith-centered behaviors. Opportunities for reflective practices, mentoring, and participation in values-related activities help learners develop deeper understanding of faith and moral responsibility. At the same time, the literature recognized that spiritual growth is difficult to measure because it often appears gradually through behaviors, attitudes, and personal reflections rather than through direct academic outcomes.

Melnick and Martínez (2021) noted that teachers often struggle with limited instructional time, large class sizes, and the need to balance academic demands with holistic development. Other challenges included the lack of teacher training, difficulty in addressing diverse emotional needs, and inconsistency in implementing SEL activities. In the area of spiritual growth, several authors emphasized challenges such as balancing children's exposure to different beliefs, maintaining students' engagement in spiritual practices, and assessing spiritual development effectively. These challenges demonstrate the need for continuous support, teacher preparation, and sustainable intervention programs.

Mondi et al. (2021) highlighted that structured programs involving mindfulness activities, mentoring, resilience training, reflection, and family involvement produce positive outcomes in learners' emotional regulation, empathy, moral grounding, and resilience. Research also emphasized that culturally responsive and context-based interventions are more effective in addressing the unique needs of learners. Overall, the reviewed literature established that social-emotional and spiritual development are interconnected dimensions of holistic education that require intentional, consistent, and sustainable support from schools, teachers, families, and communities.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design, specifically descriptive comparative in nature. A descriptive design is considered the most appropriate because the central aim is not to test causal relationships but to provide a systematic and accurate portrayal of current conditions (Creswell & Creswell, 2021). In this case, the focus on their perceptions of learners' social-emotional and spiritual development. By using descriptive methods, the study can capture prevailing trends and patterns without altering or manipulating the variable.

The choice of this design is also justified by the practical realities of the study. Since the research relied on survey questionnaires, it lends itself naturally to descriptive analysis, where data are summarized in terms of frequencies, percentages, weighted means, and standard deviations. Moreover, the inclusion of open-ended responses on challenges allows the study to have qualitative data, offering a richer picture of the barriers teachers face. These responses were analyzed connected back to the quantitative findings to propose concrete, context-based interventions.

Participants

The study involved 223 public Key Stage I teachers from Congressional District IV, Division of Batangas, who were chosen as respondents because of their direct involvement in observing and guiding learners' academic, social-emotional, and spiritual development. The sample size was determined using the Raosoft sample size calculator with a 5 percent margin of error to ensure statistical reliability and validity of the findings. To achieve proper representation across the district, the study employed stratified random sampling with proportionate allocation, allowing teachers from different sub-offices to be fairly represented while ensuring that each teacher had an equal chance of being selected.

Research Instrument

The study utilized both quantitative and qualitative data gathering instruments, primarily a Likert scale survey questionnaire and semi-structured interviews. The survey questionnaire served as the main instrument for collecting data on learners' social-emotional and spiritual growth, including self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, values and moral development, sense of purpose, respect for others' beliefs, participation in spiritual activities, and the challenges encountered by teachers. The questionnaire underwent face and content validation by experts and was pilot tested to ensure reliability through Cronbach's alpha. Responses were analyzed using weighted mean and interpreted through a four-point scale ranging from Low to High. To enrich the quantitative findings, interviews were conducted to gain deeper insights into teachers' experiences and suggested interventions. Proper ethical procedures, including informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation, were observed throughout the administration and retrieval of the instruments.

Data Collection Procedure

The study began with securing approval and permissions from the Schools Division Office of Batangas and the principals of selected schools in Congressional District IV, followed by coordination with school heads to explain the study's objectives, scope, and significance. Teacher-respondents were informed of the purpose of the study, assured of confidentiality, and asked to provide voluntary consent before participation. Data were gathered through survey questionnaires, distributed either in printed or electronic form depending on school accessibility, with sufficient time given for completion, and supplemented by short interviews with selected respondents to obtain deeper qualitative insights. Completed questionnaires were collected personally or through designated personnel, while online responses were securely stored, and interview data were recorded with consent and transcribed. All data were then tallied, scored, and analyzed in relation to the research questions, with strict observance of anonymity and ethical standards by presenting findings in aggregated form only.

Data Analysis

The data collected from surveys and interviews were organized and analyzed according to the study's objectives using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Descriptive statistics were used to describe teachers' perceptions of learners' social-emotional and spiritual growth, while inferential statistics were applied to determine significant relationships among variables. Specifically, weighted mean was used to determine the level of teachers' assessments, standard deviation measured the variability of responses, and Pearson's r coefficient of correlation was used to assess the strength and direction of the relationship between variables and test for significant associations. In addition, interview responses were thematically analyzed to identify teachers' challenges and suggested interventions.

Results

1. Social-Emotional Growth of Key Stage I Learners

1.1. *Self-awareness.*

Table 2

Level of Social-Emotional Growth of Elementary Learners in terms of Self-awareness

Self-awareness	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
My students... recognize and name their emotions during different classroom experiences.	3.14	Above Average
reflect on their feelings through activities like journaling, storytelling, or art.	3.13	Above Average
show confidence in expressing their strengths and limitations.	3.02	Above Average
demonstrate awareness of how their emotions influence their behavior.	3.12	Above Average
express pride in achievements while appreciating the accomplishments of others.	3.16	Above Average
recognize when they are stressed, anxious, or happy and identify the cause.	3.06	Above Average
set personal learning goals with optimism.	3.04	Above Average
accept feedback from teachers and peers as opportunities for growth.	3.11	Above Average
demonstrate mindfulness and focus during classroom routines.	3.08	Above Average
show curiosity and self-reflection in learning tasks.	3.08	Above Average
Composite Mean	3.09	Above Average

The findings showed that the level of self-awareness among elementary learners obtained a composite mean of 3.09 interpreted as Above Average, indicating that teachers generally perceive learners as demonstrating strong awareness of their emotions, strengths, and personal behaviors in classroom situations. The highest indicator was express pride in achievements while appreciating the accomplishments of others, which obtained a weighted mean of 3.16 interpreted as Above Average. On the other hand, the lowest indicator was show confidence in expressing their strengths and limitations, which recorded a weighted mean of 3.02 interpreted as Above Average.

1.2. *Self-management.*

Table 3

Level of Social-Emotional Growth of Elementary Learners in terms of Self-management

Self-management	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
My students... regulate their emotions by using calming strategies (e.g., deep breathing, "chill corners").	2.91	Above Average
persevere in completing difficult tasks without giving up easily.	3.00	Above Average
demonstrate self-discipline and responsibility in assigned duties.	2.93	Above Average
manage their impulses and wait for their turn.	2.91	Above Average
use positive strategies when frustrated, such as asking for help or	2.97	Above Average

pausing.		
display resilience by trying again after making mistakes.	3.01	Above Average
stay focused and attentive even when distractions are present.	2.96	Above Average
organize school materials and meet deadlines for tasks.	2.98	Above Average
adjust their behavior when reminded of class or school rules.	3.00	Above Average
balance play and work during daily routines responsibly.	3.00	Above Average
Composite Mean	2.97	Above Average

The level of self-management among elementary learners obtained a composite mean of 2.97 interpreted as Above Average, suggesting that teachers observe learners as generally able to regulate their behavior and manage their emotions in the learning environment. The highest indicator was display resilience by trying again after making mistakes, which obtained a weighted mean of 3.01 interpreted as Above Average. Meanwhile, the lowest indicators were regulate their emotions by using calming strategies (e.g., deep breathing, chill corners) and manage their impulses and wait for their turn, both obtaining a weighted mean of 2.91 interpreted as Above Average.

1.3. *Social awareness.*

Table 4

Level of Social-Emotional Growth of Elementary Learners in terms of Social Awareness

Social Awareness	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
My students...		
show empathy and kindness to peers experiencing challenges.	3.03	Above Average
participate in class discussions with respect for others' perspectives.	3.13	Above Average
recognize and value differences in culture, religion, or background.	3.04	Above Average
engage in activities that promote kindness, such as gratitude writing or community projects.	3.08	Above Average
respond with sensitivity when classmates share personal feelings.	3.08	Above Average
demonstrate fairness during games, group work, and classroom tasks.	3.09	Above Average
respect and follow school and community rules.	3.11	Above Average
offer help voluntarily to classmates in need.	3.06	Above Average
appreciate and acknowledge the contributions of others in group tasks.	3.02	Above Average
show concern for the well-being of peers and teachers.	3.09	Above Average
Composite Mean	3.07	Above Average

In terms of social awareness, the findings revealed a composite mean of 3.07 interpreted as Above Average, indicating that learners generally demonstrate empathy, fairness, and respect toward others. The highest indicator was participate in class discussions with respect for others' perspectives, which obtained a weighted mean of 3.13 interpreted as Above Average. On the other hand, the lowest indicator was appreciate and acknowledge the contributions of others in group tasks, which recorded a weighted mean of 3.02 interpreted as Above Average.

1.4. Relationship skills.

Table 5

Level of Social-Emotional Growth of Elementary Learners in terms of Relationship Skills

Relationship Skills	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
My students...		
communicate their thoughts and feelings clearly with classmates and teachers.	3.00	Above Average
cooperate effectively in group activities and projects.	3.09	Above Average
demonstrate patience, turn-taking, and respect in classroom routines.	3.01	Above Average
listen attentively when peers or teachers are speaking.	3.04	Above Average
use conflict resolution strategies to solve disagreements peacefully.	3.04	Above Average
build friendships based on trust, kindness, and respect.	3.07	Above Average
show leadership and responsibility when assigned group tasks.	3.08	Above Average
express gratitude and appreciation to others.	3.15	Above Average
seek guidance from teachers or peers when challenges arise.	3.13	Above Average
work collaboratively to achieve shared goals in school activities.	3.13	Above Average
Composite Mean	3.07	Above Average

The results also showed that the level of relationship skills among elementary learners obtained a composite mean of 3.07 interpreted as Above Average, suggesting that learners generally demonstrate positive interaction and cooperation with their peers and teachers. The highest indicator was express gratitude and appreciation to others, which obtained a weighted mean of 3.15 interpreted as Above Average. Meanwhile, the lowest indicator was communicate their thoughts and feelings clearly with classmates and teachers, which recorded a weighted mean of 3.00 interpreted as Above Average.

2. Spiritual Growth of Key Stage I Learners

2.1. Values and Moral Development

Table 6

Level of Spiritual Growth of Elementary Learners in terms of Values and Moral Development

Values and Moral Development	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
My students...		
demonstrate honesty even in small classroom situations.	2.95	Above Average
show integrity by keeping promises and taking responsibility for their actions.	3.01	Above Average
respect classroom and school rules as part of moral discipline.	2.99	Above Average
practice fairness in games, sharing, and group work.	2.98	Above Average
exhibit kindness and compassion toward classmates.	3.04	Above Average
choose to do what is right even without supervision.	3.01	Above Average
express gratitude for blessings, help, and guidance.	3.01	Above Average
show respect for authority through obedience and courtesy.	2.96	Above Average
display courage in admitting mistakes and asking for forgiveness.	3.07	Above Average
value service by helping others without expecting reward.	3.05	Above Average
Composite Mean	3.01	Above Average

The findings revealed that the level of values and moral development among elementary learners obtained a composite mean of 3.01 interpreted as Above Average, indicating that

teachers generally perceive learners as demonstrating positive moral values and ethical behaviors. The highest indicator was *display courage in admitting mistakes and asking for forgiveness*, which obtained a weighted mean of 3.07 interpreted as Above Average. Meanwhile, the lowest indicator was *demonstrate honesty even in small classroom situations*, which recorded a weighted mean of 2.95 interpreted as Above Average.

2.2. Sense of Purpose and Meaning

Table 7

Level of Spiritual Growth of Elementary Learners in terms of Sense of Purpose and Meaning

Sense of Purpose and Meaning	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
My students... express hope and optimism about their future.	2.96	Above Average
reflect on the meaning of their experiences during discussions or activities.	3.09	Above Average
set personal goals that align with positive values.	2.97	Above Average
demonstrate perseverance in challenges as part of their faith journey.	2.92	Above Average
show willingness to take responsibility in classroom or group leadership roles.	2.99	Above Average
relate lessons or stories to their own life values and choices.	3.01	Above Average
display a growing sense of ownership in spiritual practices (e.g., leading prayers).	3.00	Above Average
express discernment when faced with right and wrong decisions.	3.04	Above Average
share personal reflections about how faith or values guide their actions.	3.01	Above Average
show joy and motivation in learning that connects to deeper life meaning.	3.06	Above Average
Composite Mean	3.01	Above Average

The results showed that the level of learners' sense of purpose and meaning obtained a composite mean of 3.01 interpreted as Above Average, suggesting that learners generally demonstrate awareness of values and meaning in their experiences. The highest indicator was *reflect on the meaning of their experiences during discussions or activities*, which obtained a weighted mean of 3.09 interpreted as Above Average. On the other hand, the lowest indicator was *demonstrate perseverance in challenges as part of their faith journey*, which recorded a weighted mean of 2.92 interpreted as Above Average.

2.3. Respect for Others' Beliefs

Table 8

Level of Spiritual Growth of Elementary Learners in terms of Respect for Others' Beliefs

Respect for Others' Beliefs	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
My students... listen attentively when others share different beliefs or values.	3.00	Above Average
show respect for classmates of different faith traditions.	3.11	Above Average
avoid mocking or discriminating against peers with diverse practices.	3.04	Above Average
demonstrate sensitivity in conversations about religion or	3.00	Above Average

spirituality.		
show empathy toward classmates whose beliefs differ from their own.	3.02	Above Average
value cooperation regardless of faith or cultural background.	3.05	Above Average
express curiosity and openness when learning about other perspectives.	3.02	Above Average
recognize similarities and differences in values without judgment.	2.99	Above Average
demonstrate respect during interfaith or multicultural activities.	3.04	Above Average
treat all classmates with fairness and dignity regardless of belief system.	3.00	Above Average
Composite Mean	3.03	Above Average

In terms of respect for others' beliefs, the findings revealed a composite mean of 3.03 interpreted as Above Average, indicating that learners generally demonstrate respect toward different beliefs and perspectives. The highest indicator was *show respect for classmates of different faith traditions*, which obtained a weighted mean of 3.11 interpreted as Above Average. Meanwhile, the lowest indicator was *recognize similarities and differences in values without judgment*, which recorded a weighted mean of 2.99 interpreted as Above Average.

2.4. Spiritual or Values-Related Activities

Table 9

Level of Spiritual Growth of Elementary Learners in terms of Participation in Spiritual or Values-Related Activities

Participation in Spiritual or Values-Related Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
My students...		
participate actively in prayer or reflection activities.	2.90	Above Average
join values-formation programs or school worship gatherings.	3.01	Above Average
engage in acts of service such as helping peers or community projects.	2.93	Above Average
contribute ideas during moral or spiritual discussions.	2.95	Above Average
show enthusiasm in singing, storytelling, or role-play with moral lessons.	3.07	Above Average
take part in journaling, gratitude lists, or other reflective practices.	2.99	Above Average
volunteer in classroom routines that promote values (e.g., leading prayer).	3.09	Above Average
display interest in bible lessons, moral stories, or faith-based readings.	2.97	Above Average
engage in activities that highlight respect for creation or the environment.	3.02	Above Average
practice generosity by sharing resources or time with others.	3.04	Above Average
Composite Mean	3.00	Above Average

The results further revealed that the level of participation in spiritual or values-related activities obtained a composite mean of 3.00 interpreted as Above Average, suggesting that learners generally participate in activities related to spiritual and moral development. The highest

indicator was *volunteer in classroom routines that promote values (e.g., leading prayer)*, which obtained a weighted mean of 3.09 interpreted as Above Average. On the other hand, the lowest indicator was *participate actively in prayer or reflection activities*, which recorded a weighted mean of 2.90 interpreted as Above Average.

3. Relationship between Teachers' Assessments of Learners' Social-emotional and Spiritual Growth.

Table 10

Relationship Between the Assessments on the Social-Emotional Growth in terms of Self-awareness and on the Level of Spiritual Growth

Variables	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision on Ho	Remarks
Values and Moral Development	.651	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Sense of Purpose and Meaning	.626	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Respect for Others' Beliefs	.612	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Participation in Spiritual or Values-Related Activities	-.001	.984	No relationship	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

Coefficient of correlation (r): ±1.0 (Perfect relationship), ±.76 to .99 (Very Strong relationship), ±.51 to .75 (Strong relationship), ±.26-.50 (Moderate Relationship), ±.11 to .25 (Weak relationship), ±.01 to .10 (Very weak relationship), .00 (No relationship)

The findings revealed that self-awareness of learners has significant relationships with several dimensions of spiritual growth. Specifically, self-awareness showed a strong relationship with values and moral development ($r = .651$, $p = .000$), sense of purpose and meaning ($r = .626$, $p = .000$), and respect for others' beliefs ($r = .612$, $p = .000$). In these variables, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that the relationships were statistically significant. However, self-awareness showed no relationship with participation in spiritual or values-related activities ($r = -.001$, $p = .984$), leading to the failure to reject the null hypothesis, which indicates a not significant relationship.

Table 11

Relationship Between the Assessments on the Social-Emotional Growth in terms of Self-management and on the Level of Spiritual Growth

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision on Ho	Remarks
Values and Moral Development	.632	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Sense of Purpose and Meaning	.643	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Respect for Others' Beliefs	.620	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Participation in Spiritual or Values-Related Activities	-.054	.419	Very weak relationship	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

Coefficient of correlation (r): ±1.0 (Perfect relationship), ±.76 to .99 (Very Strong relationship), ±.51 to .75 (Strong relationship), ±.26-.50 (Moderate Relationship), ±.11 to .25 (Weak relationship), ±.01 to .10 (Very weak relationship), .00 (No relationship)

Similarly, self-management demonstrated strong relationships with values and moral development ($r = .632$, $p = .000$), sense of purpose and meaning ($r = .643$, $p = .000$), and respect for others' beliefs ($r = .620$, $p = .000$). In these areas, the null hypothesis was rejected, signifying significant relationships. On the other hand, self-management showed a very weak relationship with participation in spiritual or values-related activities ($r = -.054$, $p = .419$), which resulted in the failure to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the relationship was not significant.

Table 12

Relationship Between the Assessments on the Social-Emotional Growth in terms of Social Awareness and on the Level of Spiritual Growth

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision on Ho	Remarks
Values and Moral Development	.735	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Sense of Purpose and Meaning	.669	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Respect for Others' Beliefs	.686	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Participation in Spiritual or Values-Related Activities	-.002	.979	No relationship	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

Coefficient of correlation (r): ±1.0 (Perfect relationship), ±.76 to .99 (Very Strong relationship), ±.51 to .75 (Strong relationship), ±.26-.50 (Moderate Relationship), ±.11 to .25 (Weak relationship), ±.01 to .10 (Very weak relationship), .00 (No relationship)

Results further revealed that social awareness has strong relationships with values and moral development ($r = .735$, $p = .000$), sense of purpose and meaning ($r = .669$, $p = .000$), and respect for others' beliefs ($r = .686$, $p = .000$). For these variables, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating statistically significant relationships. However, social awareness showed no relationship with participation in spiritual or values-related activities ($r = -.002$, $p = .979$), resulting in the failure to reject the null hypothesis and indicating a not significant relationship.

Table 13

Relationship Between the Assessments on the Relationship Skills Growth in terms of Social Awareness and on the Level of Spiritual Growth

Variables	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision on Ho	Remarks
Values and Moral Development	.760	.000	Very strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Sense of Purpose and Meaning	.698	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Respect for Others' Beliefs	.685	.000	Strong relationship	Rejected	Significant
Participation in Spiritual or Values-Related Activities	-.010	.883	Very weak relationship	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

Coefficient of correlation (r): ± 1.0 (Perfect relationship), $\pm .76$ to $.99$ (Very Strong relationship), $\pm .51$ to $.75$ (Strong relationship), $\pm .26$ -. 50 (Moderate Relationship), $\pm .11$ to $.25$ (Weak relationship), $\pm .01$ to $.10$ (Very weak relationship), $.00$ (No relationship)

Lastly, relationship skills demonstrated a very strong relationship with values and moral development ($r = .760$, $p = .000$), as well as strong relationships with sense of purpose and meaning ($r = .698$, $p = .000$) and respect for others' beliefs ($r = .685$, $p = .000$). In these cases, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming that the relationships were statistically significant. However, relationship skills showed a very weak relationship with participation in spiritual or values-related activities ($r = -.010$, $p = .883$), which resulted in the failure to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the relationship was not significant.

4. Challenges Teachers Encounter in Fostering Social-emotional and Spiritual Growth among Elementary Learners.

Table 14
Challenges Teachers Encounter in Fostering Social-Emotional Growth

Challenges in Fostering Social-Emotional Growth I encounter challenges in/when...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. limited instructional time makes it difficult to integrate sel alongside academic requirements.	3.06	Agree
2. sel is treated as an “extra subject” rather than embedded in daily lessons.	3.00	Agree
3. due to lack structured training and support in handling emotional and behavioral issues.	2.96	Agree
4. to sustain consistency in reinforcing sel strategies throughout the school day.	2.97	Agree
5. managing diverse emotional expressions and readiness levels among students is overwhelming.	3.06	Agree
6. building trusting relationships with every student is difficult due to class size and time limits.	3.04	Agree
7. maintaining warmth and empathy in stressful or disruptive classroom situations is challenging.	3.00	Agree
8. creating safe, nonjudgmental spaces for emotional expression is hindered by peer teasing or exclusion.	2.95	Agree
9. standardized testing and curriculum pressures reduce focus on SEL activities.	3.04	Agree
10. embedding SEL into academic subjects requires additional effort and creativity that is hard to sustain.	3.04	Agree
Composite Mean	3.01	Agree

Findings revealed that teachers generally agree that they encounter challenges in fostering social-emotional growth among elementary learners, as reflected in the composite mean of 3.01 interpreted as Agree. The highest indicators, both obtaining a weighted mean of 3.06 interpreted as Agree, were limited instructional time makes it difficult to integrate SEL alongside academic requirements and managing diverse emotional expressions and readiness levels among students is overwhelming. Meanwhile, the lowest indicator was creating safe, nonjudgmental spaces for emotional expression is hindered by peer teasing or exclusion, which recorded a weighted mean of 2.95 interpreted as Agree.

Table 15
Challenges do Teachers Encounter in Fostering Spiritual Growth

Challenges in Fostering Spiritual Growth I encounter challenges in...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. balancing children’s exposure to secular ideas with their spiritual formation is difficult.	2.96	Agree
2. deciding when and how to give learners responsibility for their faith journey is uncertain.	3.06	Agree
3. some children show disinterest or doubt, leaving me feeling powerless in guiding growth.	2.95	Agree

4. preschool and younger children's capacity for deeper spiritual truths is often underestimated.	2.91	Agree
5. designing age-appropriate yet theologically rich lessons is challenging.	3.00	Agree
6. measuring spiritual growth is difficult since it often shows in subtle, intangible ways.	2.99	Agree
7. the slow and unpredictable nature of spiritual development makes progress hard to track.	3.00	Agree
8. instruction alone does not guarantee spiritual maturity, making modeling and mentoring essential but time-consuming.	3.01	Agree
9. competing cultural and media influences sometimes weaken students' commitment to values and faith.	3.04	Agree
10. maintaining consistency in family and school routines for spiritual practices is difficult due to parental or systemic constraints.	3.05	Agree
Composite Mean	3.00	Agree

Similarly, teachers generally agreed that they encounter challenges in fostering spiritual growth among elementary learners, as shown in the composite mean of 3.00 interpreted as Agree. The highest indicator was deciding when and how to give learners responsibility for their faith journey is uncertain, which obtained a weighted mean of 3.06 interpreted as Agree. This was followed by maintaining consistency in family and school routines for spiritual practices is difficult due to parental or systemic constraints, with a weighted mean of 3.05 interpreted as Agree. On the other hand, the lowest indicator was preschool and younger children's capacity for deeper spiritual truths is often underestimated, which recorded a weighted mean of 2.91 interpreted as Agree.

5. Proposed Intervention Activities

Sustainable Development Activity 1

Title: Calm Corner and Breathing Pause Activity

Objective

The activity aims to help learners develop the ability to regulate their emotions by using calming strategies such as deep breathing, pausing, and self-reflection when they experience frustration, excitement, or stress during classroom situations.

Expected Outcomes

Through this activity, learners are expected to develop greater emotional awareness and self-regulation skills. They will learn to recognize their emotional responses and apply calming strategies before reacting impulsively. Over time, learners may demonstrate improved emotional control, patience, and readiness to return to learning tasks after managing their feelings.

Sustainable Development Activity 2

Title: My Turn, Your Turn: Practicing Patience and Impulse Control

Objective

This activity aims to help learners develop impulse control and patience by practicing turn-taking and waiting appropriately during classroom interactions and activities.

Expected Outcomes

Learners are expected to demonstrate improved patience, impulse control, and respect for others during classroom interactions. They will learn to regulate their responses and wait appropriately for their turn during discussions and group activities.

Sustainable Development Activity 3

Title: Celebrating Teamwork: Recognizing Everyone's Contribution

Objective

This activity aims to encourage learners to appreciate and acknowledge the contributions of their classmates during collaborative tasks and group activities.

Expected Outcomes

Learners are expected to develop a greater appreciation for teamwork and recognize the value of their peers' contributions. This activity promotes respect, empathy, and collaborative responsibility during group learning experiences.

Sustainable Development Activity 4

Title: Speak from the Heart: Expressing Thoughts and Feelings

Objective

This activity aims to help learners communicate their thoughts and feelings clearly and respectfully with classmates and teachers.

Expected Outcomes

Learners are expected to improve their ability to express their thoughts and emotions clearly while maintaining respect for others. This activity encourages open communication, emotional awareness, and stronger interpersonal relationships in the classroom.

Sustainable Development Activity 5

Title: Truth Matters: Practicing Honesty in Everyday Situations

Objective

This activity aims to help learners develop honesty and integrity in small classroom situations by encouraging them to admit mistakes and practice truthful behavior.

Expected Outcomes

Learners are expected to develop a stronger sense of honesty and responsibility in their everyday actions. They will learn to admit mistakes, accept consequences, and value truthfulness in their interactions with others.

Sustainable Development Activity 6

Title: Never Give Up: Building Perseverance in Challenges

Objective

This activity aims to help learners develop perseverance and resilience when facing challenges, helping them continue working toward their goals even when tasks become difficult.

Expected Outcomes

Learners are expected to develop greater persistence and confidence when facing challenges. They will learn that effort and determination can help them overcome difficulties and achieve their goals.

Sustainable Development Activity 7

Title: Understanding Differences: Respecting Diverse Beliefs

Objective

This activity aims to help learners recognize and respect similarities and differences in beliefs, traditions, and values among their classmates.

Expected Outcomes

Learners are expected to develop openness, empathy, and respect toward classmates who may have different beliefs or backgrounds. This activity promotes understanding and acceptance within the classroom community.

Sustainable Development Activity 8

Title: Quiet Reflection Time

Objective

This activity aims to encourage learners to actively participate in prayer, reflection, or quiet moments of gratitude as part of their daily classroom routine.

Expected Outcomes

Learners are expected to develop deeper engagement in reflective practices and values-related activities. Through regular reflection, they may become more aware of their actions, feelings, and responsibilities toward others.

4. Discussion

The study was conducted to examine the social-emotional and spiritual growth of elementary learners as perceived by their teachers. It specifically aimed to determine the level of learners' development in terms of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship skills, as well as aspects of spiritual growth, including values and moral development, sense of purpose and meaning, respect for others' beliefs, and participation in spiritual or values-related activities.

In addition, the study explored the challenges encountered by teachers in fostering these dimensions of development and determined whether there is a significant relationship between social-emotional competencies and spiritual growth. The findings were intended to serve as the basis for proposing enhancement activities that could further strengthen learners' holistic development in the classroom.

To achieve these objectives, the study utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. Elementary school teachers served as the respondents since they regularly observe learners' behaviors and interactions in the classroom. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire that measured the different indicators of social-emotional and spiritual development, as well as the challenges teachers experience in nurturing these qualities among their students. The responses were analyzed using weighted mean to determine the level of manifestation of the indicators and Pearson correlation to identify relationships between the variables.

5. Conclusion

From the analysis of the results, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. Teachers assessed that elementary learners demonstrate above average level of social-emotional growth in terms of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship skills.

2. Teachers assessed that elementary learners demonstrate above average level of spiritual growth in terms of values and moral development, sense of purpose and meaning, respect for others' beliefs, and participation in spiritual or values-related activities.

3. Social-emotional growth variables of learners are significantly related to values and moral development, sense of purpose and meaning, and respect for others' beliefs, while participation in spiritual or values-related activities does not show a significant relationship with the social-emotional growth variables.

4. Teachers encounter several challenges in sustaining the social-emotional and spiritual growth among elementary learners. In social-emotional development, limited instructional time makes it difficult to integrate SEL alongside academic requirements, and managing diverse emotional expressions and readiness levels among students is overwhelming. In spiritual development, deciding when and how to give learners responsibility for their faith journey is uncertain, and maintaining consistency in family and school routines for spiritual practices is difficult due to parental or systemic constraints. Overall, these challenges show the difficulty of sustaining and maintaining learners' holistic development.

5. Sustainable development activities focusing on strengthening selected social-emotional and spiritual competencies were developed as a basis for sustaining the holistic development of Key Stage I learners.

References

- Albers, C. (2023, May 31). *Nurturing spiritual development in children – ETB #167*. Equipped To Be Podcast. <https://conniealbers.com/nurturing-spiritual-development-in-children-etb-167>
- Foundation Worldview. (2025, January 28). *Encouraging spiritual growth in kids*. Foundation Worldview. <https://foundationworldview.com>
- Ho, J., & Funk, S. (2023, March). Promoting young children’s social and emotional health. *Young Children*, 73(1). National Association for the Education of Young Children. <https://www.naeyc.org>
- Melnick, H., & Martínez, L. (2021, September 18). How one elementary school integrates social-emotional skills in the classroom. Learning Policy Institute. <https://learningpolicyinstitute.org>
- Mondi, C. F., Giovanelli, A., & Reynolds, A. J. (2021). Fostering socio-emotional learning through early childhood intervention. *International Journal of Child Care and Education Policy*, 15(6). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40723-021-00084-8>
- Weissberg, R., Durlak, J. A., Domitrovich, C. E., & Gullotta, T. P. (2022, February 15). Why social and emotional learning is essential for students. *Edutopia*. George Lucas Educational Foundation. <https://www.edutopia.org/>